
Herramientas para una descarbonización más rápida en construcciones y industrias con algoritmos multiagentes y de optimización: una revisión

Tools to provide faster decarbonization in buildings and industries with multi-agents and optimization algorithms: A review

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RESUMEN. Las herramientas para lograr la neutralidad de carbono son vitales para proyectos de construcción e instalaciones industriales cuyo objetivo principal es reducir el alto impacto ambiental asociado a regulaciones más estrictas en diversos países. Estas herramientas son cruciales para reducir las emisiones atmosféricas y mejorar la calidad del aire en los centros urbanos. Este artículo de revisión propone un análisis comparativo de diferentes modelos de sistemas multiagente que aumentan la eficiencia energética de los edificios y optimizan la fabricación, permitiendo una descarbonización más rápida en ambas actividades. El objetivo de esta revisión es presentar un recurso que permita mejorar estas técnicas o integrar diferentes algoritmos de los artículos citados, permitiendo a otros científicos mejorar el rendimiento mediante el desarrollo de estos modelos en futuros artículos. Los resultados se describen en tablas comparativas que presentan los métodos utilizados y su aplicación, facilitando una rápida revisión de las referencias que han aplicado sistemas multiagente en entornos de construcción e industriales. Se concluye que la aplicación de sistemas multiagente puede reducir el consumo energético y los costos recurrentes de estos sitios asociados a la mitigación de emisiones, y son herramientas que están avanzando con el tiempo con un mejor rendimiento y pueden ser vitales para el objetivo de neutralización de carbono de estas dos actividades aun potencialmente contaminantes.

Palabras clave. *Herramientas multiagente, Proyectos de construcción e instalaciones industriales, Neutralidad de carbono*

ABSTRACT. Tools for achieving carbon neutrality are vital for construction and industrial projects whose primary goals are to reduce the high environmental impact of these projects, associated with stricter regulations in various countries. These tools are crucial for reducing atmospheric emissions and improving air quality in urban centers. This review article proposes a comparative analysis of different multi-agent system models that increase the energy efficiency of buildings and optimize manufacturing, enabling decarbonization in both activities to be achieved more quickly. The objective of this review is to present a resource that enables the improvement of these techniques or the integration of different algorithms from the cited articles, enabling other scientists to improve performance by developing these models in future articles. The results are described in comparative tables that present the methods used and their application, facilitating a quick overview of references that have applied multi-agent systems in construction and industrial settings. It is concluded that the application of multi-agent systems can reduce energy consumption and recurring costs of these sites associated with emissions mitigation and are tools that are advancing over the years with better performance and can be vital in the goal of carbon neutralization of these two still potentially polluting activities.

Keywords. Multi-agent tools, Construction projects and industrial facilities, Carbon neutrality

1. Introduction

The development of an industrial platform to minimize carbon dioxide emissions based on the insights of autonomous agents that evaluate key task scheduling factors, historical emissions data, and machine tool

patterns through IoT contributes to optimization capabilities, addressing emissions mitigation with resource production based on organizational dynamics responses, with greater precision in decision-making in the event of unexpected events [1].

Multi-agent systems are a platform for data acquisition and local decision-making to solve complex problems with agility and adaptability. They can be applied in micro and macro contexts, providing a tool for decarbonization strategies [2].

The integration of IoT devices, cloud computing, autonomous data analytics, and multi-agent systems provides collaborative synergy in greenhouse gas emissions mitigation across industries, exploring an adaptive measurement framework for standardizations that rapidly achieve goals and scalability in the integration architecture between these systems [3].

Applying optimization models within industries is a challenge across multiple segments, balancing multinational economic competitiveness with sustainability by evaluating technological options, production, marketing, and emissions price functions, and assessing the economic feasibility of adopting emerging technologies with high carbon capture potential within different industrial operating processes based on industrial and government policies [4].

Evaluating the dynamics of the carbon trading market and improving the cost-effectiveness of incentive mechanisms to achieve emission reduction targets, verify auctions and increase the adoption of low-carbon technologies is also one of the scopes of the system, as carried out by [5], who carried out this application in companies working with power plants in China in the development of a multi-agent system with reinforcement learning.

The impacts of policies on carbon capture and storage pathways through subsidy policies can be estimated within a multi-agent system, determining tariffs that promote greater diffusion in different regions and reduce the cost of mitigation or greater emission reductions for industries with high environmental impact, such as cement [6].

The interaction between the individual objectives of different participants in the carbon and electricity market, with micro and macro perspectives on different trading models, can be evaluated using multi-agent modeling, which provides strategies with greater benefits in price evaluation by improving the coordination of relationships between multiple markets simultaneously in optimal trading scheduling [7].

The evaluation of carbon capture and utilization technologies in microgrids for peer-to-peer energy

sharing, to reduce costs and mitigate emissions using a multi-agent policy optimization algorithm, has the potential to provide management actions within a highly efficient coordination model [8].

Large companies are the first to adopt a low-carbon economy thanks to their technical and financial advantages, in addition to increasing their exports in markets with greater environmental demands [9].

Using multi-agent systems and an evolutionary game simulation, was verified how different variables affect carbon capture and storage strategies through diverse behavioral dynamics. This allows select the optimal strategy, determine equilibrium points, stability, and the most representative parameters for achieving high emission mitigation rates [10].

Accurately determining and predicting, based on time series and multi-agent systems, the trading patterns, price volatility, and adoption dynamics of different emerging carbon dioxide capture technologies contributes to reducing uncertainty levels for low-carbon energy transitions in small and large companies and improves short-term emission reductions [11].

Based on the indication of emissions and carbon neutrality targets in the 30 provinces of China, a multi-agent game can be developed within the platform, as [12] did, with the objective of verifying which could be the best decarbonization strategies within an evolutionary process in different industries that allows assigning peaks of carbon neutrality achievement from different emerging technologies such as biochar production, energy generation routes with carbon capture and storage, presenting different environmental and economic routes for experts within the industries to outline business sustainability strategies, presenting different scenarios and possibilities of preconfigured settings and also allowing manual configuration to experts.

Platforms like the SEND system are a testbed for exploring smart energy generation and distribution. It allows campus system operators to control how renewable energy sources are self-consumed into the distribution grid and feed excess generation into the grid. It also optimizes energy use on the university campus by measuring the grid's carbon intensity. The attribution of technical and geographic information enables energy flow and optimized routing of storage and cogeneration. Researchers and system operators can test new

algorithms, methodologies, and cutting-edge resolutions for energy distribution in a closed environment with energy-conscious consumers [13].

Carbon price prediction models can be developed from the integration of recurrent neural networks, genetic algorithms, multi-agent systems and evolutionary game theories, being highly accurate in mid-term predictions and strong heterogeneity, presenting capacity to analyse prices changes in different risk preferences features [14].

Diverse tools to provide faster decarbonization in different industries are being developed in the university, describe these different innovations in a review, collaborate to understand and disclose alternatives for each segment of industry and adjust associations and improvement of the developed technologies.

2. Material and Methods

This review will present a comparative analysis of multi-agent system models in the context of emission reduction for buildings and different industries. The research tool used will be Google Scholar, based on articles in scientific journals presenting specific technologies and their application areas.

The development of comparative tables that allow a quick visualization of the energy efficiency achieved by each of the algorithms integrated with the multi-agent systems presents application paths for achieving carbon neutrality in buildings and industries, enabling the improvement of these techniques or the integration of different articles by other scientists to improve the performance of models developed in future articles.

Scale distributed energy resources that improve energy efficiency, reduce carbon emissions and enhance grid resilience in building or industries applying multi-agent frameworks was presented in a review of the state of art which was made by [15] that summarized and analyse future perspectives.

Evaluate different applications for algorithms in a review help to expand, adress challenges and highlight extensive potential and relevance for current and future technological contexts as presented by [16] that show diverse application scenarios to multiagent frameworks.

Combine different technologies and present gains are described by [17] for multiagent systems and artificial intelligence of things that will be made in this review too.

3. Results and Discussions

Different size of building could achieve lower atmospheric emissions with the reduction in the energy consumption, incorporating modular and flexible as multi-agents control for heating, ventilation and air-conditioning. Associate genetic algorithm, integer linear programming method and multi-agent has potential to reduce the carbon footprint by 23.4% of a winter test day in the multi-zone buildings[18]. It was presented in the table 1 some multiagent algorithms with their energy efficiency reached for your insertion in the building network.

Optimization focused in global optimization for datacenters, applying multi-agent deep reinforcement learning that adjust computational workload, waste heat utilization and battery charging/discharging capacity reduce the total electricity consumption by 4.01% as the operation cost by 9.78% compared with non-optimization, decreasing the grid electricity consumption [19].

For wider adoption of digital technologies as IoT devices and AI Software for decarbonization in environmental management, it is crucial develop innovative finance models, training programs and compatibility with different providers[20].

A transaction mechanism that promote dual incentive demand response about carbon price information and compensation, reduced carbon emission by 15.4% for a specif stakeholder and improve the revenue of energy generation operator with a multiagent game optimal scheduling, resulting in an environmental and economical application [21].

The most efficient ways to reduce the carbon emission in the buildings and industries consist in two phases that are reduce the energy demand and replace fossil based source for renewable energy resulting in research, significant emission reduction achieved up to 70% [22].

Multiagent systems for energy management is an emerging technology included in the role of energy digitalization that provide high efficiency, low carbon and intelligent building with advanced model predictive controls and collaborate with the integration of these in smart cities as increase the resilience and flexibility for climate change adaption [23].

Ensure safety and promote superior performance of energy efficiency and pollutant emission reduciore are some of the tasks attributed in a multiagent system [24]

Table 1. Multi-agent methods to improve energy efficiency in buildings

Method	Building	Energy efficiency reached	Ref.
Multi-agent system consisting in prediction agent, sensing agent of a Fuzzy system as a rule base in a ZigBee network	Higher education institution	Reduction of 3% in energy consumption of HVAC	[25]
Multi-agent deep reinforcement learning	Grid responsive building	Reduction of over 6% net load demand compared to standard reinforcement learning approaches	[26]
Attention-based multi-agent deep reinforcement learning	Office building	Reduce energy consumption by 0.7% until 4.18%	[27]
Multi-agent system based coordinated optimal load scheduling	Building cluster	Reduce the peak power by 5.54% without increasing electricity costs and carbon emissions	Zhang et al,2023 [28]
Context-aware multi-agent recommendation system	Residential building	Provide energy cost savings of 18% and more for most studied households, as reduce a significant CO2 emissions	[29]

Source: Authors

Demand response management that ensure the production requirement in the automotive industry with explainable multi-agent deep reinforcement learning focused on a day-ahead production scheduling save up to additional 13.6 and 30.7% of energy costs in a automotive assembly for one day and three day prediction horizons applying decomposed multi-agent deep Q-network, determining the best plan under various weather and electricity price conditions promoting a sustainable manufacturing[30].

Mixed-integer-linear-programming model to achieve net zero of carbon dioxide emission target for hard-to-abate industries as chemical,steel and cement has potential to achieve a reduction of up to 20% [31].

A stable connection is crucial for the message exchange between agents and implementate redundant communication contribute with the overall stability, reducing the susceptibility of errors. Multiagent system allow online reconfigurations, adapting with the production control [32].

Machining parameters optimization based in multiagent reinforcement learning with reward function, contributing in the production efficiency considering spindle and feed speed as variables with Markov decision problem on a feasible region, improving prediction performance and reaching optimization effect improved by 13% and time saved [33].

Multi-agent deep deterministic policy gradient algorithm evaluate bidding strategies and solve problems with incomplete market information and game behavior of electricity generator companies, verifying that traditional carbon auction mechanism under long-term net zero goal and consignment auction in short-term carbon peak goal [34].

The technological progress will be the main reason for the reduction in the emission prediction analysis of 14 different industries in China with non linear multi-agent intertemporal model, presenting a MAPE value of 1.81% from energy consumption and emission forecasting [35].

Design eco-friendly materials as a high ultra performance concrete incorporating solid wastes from multi-agent framework was made by [36] that applied the collaboration framework and constructed a knowledge graph identifying feasible pathways to perform the objective and reduce the carbon footprint of the cement industry.

Mathematical models as multi objective optimization method evaluate trade-off between different objective in conflict for costs, emissions and energy reduction,

analysing the performance of different metrics being a powerful tool for industrial processes [37].

Adjust the supply chain structure applying multiobjective optimization could decrease carbon emission and aggregate economic growth [38].

Multi objective optimization integrated with multi criteria decision making has a great potential to refine supplier evaluation in different industries based on green and resilient index and as consequence reduce carbon emission [39]. This being evaluated by table 2 with optimization models in different segment of industries.

Find optimal scenario and emission reduction rate recommended with the costs in the coal industry can be evaluated by a multiobjective superstructure optimization model [40].

Achieve the highest greenhouse gas emission reduction in the harvested wood products for this industry with the distribution optimally across value chains to climate change mitigation can be obtained by multiobjective optimization approach [41].

Determine the economy efficiency of biodegradable plastics in relation of geographical advantages and carbon emission reduction would be implemented in large scale with NSGA-III and Pareto optimal solution improving the profit of polymer industry and minimize environmental pollution [42].

Integrate multiobjective programming with activity based costing (ABC) and theory of constraints (TOC) evaluating carbon tax costs becomes a tool to decision making model to determine the optimal carbon emission reduction and profits in different manufacturing industries [43].

Investigate specific weights yields improvement associating improved environmental impact and minimal project value loss considering uncertain factors and several objectives in the norwegian petroleum industry about electrification is a excellent task to be implemented with multiobjective optimization [44].

Process layout is crucial for operational costs, manufacturing efficiency and emission reduction and this optimization can be implemented with mixed integer non linear programming (MINLP) through General Algebraic Modeling System for food, chemical, polymer and biofuel industries [45].

In the automotive industries apply a multiobjective optimization model could evaluate three functions that are social advantages maximisation, cost minimisation, and emission minimisation with an interconnected prediction-based dynamic non-dominated sorting algorithm (ICP-DNSGA-II) for supply chain [46].

Table 2. Optimization models to reduce emission of the industries

Method	Industry	Emission mitigation reached	Ref.
Multi objective optimization framework employing the NSGA-II (Non-dominated Sorting Genetic Algorithm - II) algorithm	Eco-Industrial-Park represented by electronic equipment, automobile manufacturing, communication factories.	Carbon emission intensity drops by 27.29 % in 2025 and 45.64 % in 2030	[47]
Integrated the methods of material flow analysis (MFA), supply and demand matching (SDM), NSGA-II and conservation supply curve (CSC)	Industrial-Park consisting by equipment manufacturing, steel, aluminium, electric power and cement industries	Carbon emission reduction of integrated scenario had 65% reduction rate	[48]
Mixed Integer Linear Programming (MILP)	Additive manufacturing	Carbon emission value of 138 tCO ₂ e reduced by 128 tCO ₂ e	[49]
MILP energy optimization model	Shanghai Industrial Park	61 % reduction in emission compared with the baseline	[50]
Multi-objective optimization with NSGA-II introducing a dimensionality reduction technique	Iron and Steel Industry	33% reduction in emission of CO ₂ applied in 25 process-equipments	[51]

These multiagent system and multi objective optimization models cited in this paper can be associated to develop a new algorithm for a specific segment of industry to promote faster emission mitigation. The integration of both was presented by [52] in the textile manufacturing process, performing better for this process than traditional approaches.

Carbon capture, utilization and storage is developed faster with agent based modelling, presenting potential to evaluate large scale systems as presented by [53] that performed the simulation in the multimodal infrastructure of the United States.

4. Conclusion

This scientific paper contribute as a survey for researchers that aim develop a multiagent system to reduce pollutant emissions with different factor of energy efficiency and carbon emission reduction reached for different algorithms.

Some limitations for multiagent can be implemented with optimization algorithms as related in this paper for higher complexity scale as attributed in smart cities or larger complex of industries or factories in different locations.

The relevance for the scientific community is present a novel review about different algorithms aggregated to accelerate decarbonization.

Methodology of these related works cited can be applied as reference for future developed algorithms to promote faster carbon emission mitigation.

Future works could evaluate and specific one of the algorithms cited in this paper to present a extended literature in different segment of industries.

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CONFLICT OF INTEREST

The authors declare that they have no conflict of interest.

CONTRIBUTION AND APPROVAL OF THE AUTHORS

William Gouvêa Buratto: Conceptualization, methodology, writing, and editing.

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Gabriel Villarrubia González: writing and preparation of the original draft.

"All authors affirm that they have read and approved the final version of this article."

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